

More public and community communication regarding forest fires in Loja

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The environmental and human catastrophe resulting from the scourges of forests and mountains in southern Ecuador demands greater quantity and quality of information to guide the community, reduce the impacts, and organize recovery plans.

From other experiences, it is known that people seek to communicate, learn how to act, where to gather, and the clear evacuation routes. This information is usually received through the radio. The transmission antennas for cellular phone signals or electrical networks become disabled; there is more efficiency through direct messages from the radio.

On the other hand, private media and social media platforms contribute to links and dissemination, but those with competencies and penetration in rural sectors are public and community media. This implies strengthening broadcasts, providing space for multiple testimonies, and showing all the human facets of events.

Furthermore, it is legally the responsibility of governments to make information transparent and accessible to citizens because it is the right of individuals to know what and how the relevant authority proceeds; it is part of freedom of expression. Not providing public information is to contravene the laws, but above all, it is to disregard human dignity.

It will take months, years, for the recovery of the forests of Loja; there will be other losses, and a path to the recovery of ecosystems begins. Therefore, it is very urgent to start a public communication process to learn new ways of coexisting, ways to care for and monitor the environment, and to inaugurate creative industries that provide jobs for hundreds of families who are losing their livelihoods.

I hope that the public and community media in Loja, starting today, become less governmental and private to be authentically popular, and project the voices of those who have problems and also propose solutions.